

ECONOMIC LIFE OF ANCIENT CHINA.

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Annotation. This article provides information about the economic life of China in the early centuries BC, Chinese civilization, trade relations and their characteristics, as well as how Chinese economy developed under the empires.

Keywords: civilization, Juanxe River, Yanszi River, irrigation farming, mulberry tree, water Carpenter

As the Chinese state talks about economic life, first of all, the formation and civilizational place of this state is very important: the ancient Chinese civilization is the land. In the 1st century BC, V-III was formed in the millennia in the middle reaches of the Juanxe River, closed for a long time. Any state development located by the sea or river is natural. Especially agriculture and livestock farming. Water is important in the development of these farms. The territory of China in particular its Xuanxe River has long been covered with thick forests. Even today, China is characterized by the size of its forest areas. [1] the earth is inhabited by Rhino, tapir, bamboo rats in the middle reaches of the Juanxe River in the millennia BC., a bamboo tree grew. The Valley's soft alluvial soil made it suitable for farming. The improvement of the first pottery processing and labor weapons in society will certainly lead to an increase in excess product. Er. II. by the beginning of the millennium BC, the population living along the banks of the Juanxe and Yanszi Rivers is wider than metal used. [2] the widespread use of metal, increased labor activity, improved tillage, and new forms created favorable conditions for irrigation farming. As a result of the increase in yield, there was a property stratification.

Farming has long been considered an attentive and proud profession in China. Therefore, mainly rye and wheat were grown. Over time, the Chinese population began to grow rice, rice seeds are brought from India. [3] from this we can see that from time immemorial, these two countries have established relations of exchange and trade between China and India. Around the world, the tea we eat in love also originated in China. Mulberry cultivation was one of the main occupations of the Chinese population. [3] in early spring Moss, all trees are green in color. At this age, with the help of a mulberry tree leaf, silkworms begin to be fed. Silkworm envelops the fibers of the cocoon and is incredibly valuable to us, silk is made, which is soft and elegant.

Farming, hog, dog farming were the main occupation.[4] by now, the Chinese fauna is very rich and diverse. There are more than 1,000 species of vertebrates and birds. Each animal species lives in zones according to its habitat.

Er. in the 1st century BC. In the second half of the millennium, with the help of a pottery hammer, an improved form of Sickles and knives in agriculture arose. This caused the stratification to accelerate. The ancient Chinese were very well aware of the application of their scientific knowledge in agriculture, animal husbandry, handicrafts and other fields. In this case, on the territory of China, as in the territory of each state, there are places with desertification, mountain, pasture, difficult to get out of water. They are irrigation facilities invented in other states: water carpeting, shell water facilities, Dargam, Zagariq, Those who invented structures similar to bozsuv channels with the help of their knowledge, skills. Irrigation facilities have made a significant contribution to the development of Agriculture.

By the time of the in nobility Association was led by Van. Clan rule was in the hands of his elder and clan-nobles. The clan-the main part of the tribe-were simple communal farmers. Those who did not have their own land, the peasants were forced to work on the noble land and pay a certain part of the cultivated crop to the noble as a tax.

In the Van era, due to belonging to one layer or another, the external lifestyle of a person and his family is very strictly defined. While the culture of accommodation, repair, interaction between people, dress code, nutrition was strict, now the opposite is true. In the XXI century, monand developed everything: production enterprises, technology-technology, culture, mentality. No one can limit these procedures as in the previous darv.

The Zhou society was formed from the oqsuyaks, who distinguished themselves from the people. As always, the trade and trade were handled by the common people. The order of ownership of land was general and evenly distributed among the family. If the family is large, all children are united under the ownership of the father, the property is not divided even after the death of the head of the family.

Er. in the 1st century BC. Social stratification became more complicated at the end of the VIII century. This led to an increase in the number of slaves and dependent populations. Trade, goods, production, monetary relations grew. The lands were divided by Van into nobles, military, Noble. The introduction of private ownership of the land caused the formation of the rich even among the common people. Now, as before, they are not interested in their socio-economic life and

position, as a result, rural traditions have weakened. From here we can see that a person becomes dissatisfied with his previous lifestyle after his economic situation begins to improve. It has long been formed into our blood.

Er. in the 1st century BC. From 202 BC until the III century AD, the Han Empire ruled. In the early period when this empire came to power, the state of the people improved: taxes were reduced, slaves were freed, privileges were granted, freedom was given to production, trade, punishment for insults was abolished as well as an increase in the population. Under Han, the state developed in every way. It was during this period that the Great Silk Road, which went to the whole world with grain, connected the East and the West, arose.

During the administration of the Tan empire, all land in China was declared state-owned. [5] a certain amount of land was leased to all farmers during this period. Now each peasant could sell his own, plant any type of product he wanted. But public land could not be sold. Peasants passed obligations along with taxes at the expense of state land.

In conclusion, we can say that in ancient times, the occurrence, formation, development of any state will not be its own development. But the fact that the Chinese rulers could not follow a rational policy, that the lands were only in the hands of wealthy nobles, heavy taxes, the pressure of the nobility on the common people, the enslavement of the population stole the plight of the people. The peasants suffered mainly from this. Nevertheless, the XXI became a great country of the century, ranked among the progressive, developed countries.

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